

A NEW SPECIES OF THE GENUS *BUTHOTUS* VACHON (ARACHNIDA: SCORPIONIDA: BUTHIDAE) FROM PAKISTAN WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CHROMATOGRAPHY AND ELECTROPHORESIS OF ITS VENOM

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ABSTRACT

A new species of the genus *Buthotus* Vachon is described from Moro, Sindh, Pakistan with special reference to its male genitalia, Gel chromatography and electrophoresis of the venom. This species is compared with its closest allies and the relationships is briefly discussed using apomorphic characters

Key word: New species, *Buthotus*, Scorpionida, chromatography, electrophoresis, Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Buthotus* first time described by Vachon (1949) from Ethiopian and Oriental regions, with type species *B. judaicus* Simon. Tikader and Bastawade (1983) in their fauna of India described only one species *Buthotus alticola punjabensis* (Birula) which were formerly placed under the genus *Buthus* by Pocock (1900). Vachon (1950) synonymised under the genus *Buthotus*.

Presently a new species *Buthotus asimii* is described from Moro, Sindh Pakistan which is closely allied to *B. alticola punjabensis* (Birula) and isolated from the same by its apomorphic characters.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The animals were collected from Moro Sindh, Pakistan and were killed with formalin and preserved in 70% Alcohol. For the study of male genitalia the specimens were dissected out by removing the tergites of mesosoma. After dissection the aedeagus was mounted on slide then taken the photograph using Photographic microscope.

For the study of electrophoresis and chromatography the technique generally followed by Amir *et al.* (1994 a, b, c, d and 2003).

Buthotus asimii sp.n.
(Figs. 1 to 3)

Colouration:

Body generally reddish brown.

Prosoma:

Carapace: Entire surface of carapace granular, all carinae granular, ocular tubercles black and dark black, anterior margins granular and provided with 22-24 small brownish setae, lateral margins crenulated but more crenulated on anterior portion.

Pedipalp (Fig. 2B):

Manus slender, stout, longer than femur shorter than carapace. Almost all carinae weak and smooth outer and anterior side provided with a crenulated crest of 12-13 denticular tubercles. Patella longer than femur but always shorter than carapace, inner or anterior surface provided almost granular crest with 12 sub-denticular tubercles. Manus or hand globular and length of underhand shorter than femur. Fixed finger almost as long as femur but

movable finger longer than carapace, dentitions on the fingers consisting of two rows of non-imbricated teeth granular on the fixed and movable finger. Trichobothrial pattern of pedipalp 'B' type.

Table 1. Measurement in cm/mm meristic characters of the male holotype *Buthotus asimii* sp.n.

Character	Holotype Male
Total length	3.4 cm
Carapace length	0.5 cm
Mesosoma length	0.9 cm
Metasoma length	2.0 cm
I segment length/width	0.3/0.2 cm
II segment length/width	0.35/0.25 cm
III segment length/width	0.4/0.28 cm
IV segment length/width	0.45/0.3 cm
V segment length/width	0.5/0.3 cm
Telson length	0.6 cm
Vesicle length/width	0.35/0.28 cm
Aculeus length	0.25 cm
Pedipalp length	1.4 cm
Femur length/width	0.3/0.1 cm
Patella length/width	0.4/0.2 cm
Chela length/width	0.7/0.3 cm
Fixed finger length	0.35 cm
Movable finger length	0.4 cm
Chelicera, Chela length/width	0.2/0.1 cm
Fixed finger length	0.12 cm
Movable finger length	0.14 cm
Pectinal tooth count	30
Male Genitalia	2.5 mm

Table 2. Variation in tarsomere II spine counts in *Buthotus asimii* sp.n. on each specimen, the spine of the left and right legs of each pair were counted.

Legs	Margin	4	5	6	7	8
I	Prolateral	6	5	3	4	5
	Retrolateral	7	6	5	4	8
II	Prolateral	4	3	7	5	6
	Retrolateral	3	4	5	7	6
III	Prolateral	5	3	4	5	4
	Retrolateral	7	6	3	5	5
IV	Prolateral	8	2	7	4	6
	Retrolateral	9	5	6	5	7

Fig.1. *Buthotus asimii*; A. dorsal view, B. ventral view.

Legs (Fig. 2C):

Femur with patella smooth and carinae crenulated. Tibia with strong tibial spurs, on the legs III and IV, size 0.1 cm, shape of pedal spurs spiny, tarsomere I laterally flat hairy and not provided with setae on dorsal and ventral margins, tarsomere II conical shape.

Pectines (Fig. 2E):

Pectines well developed and almost two times longer than wide, nine middle lamellae present, fulcra nearly triangular covered with small microscopic hairs, pectinal teeth light brown with 30 teeth.

Genital operculum (Fig 2F):

Genital operculum wider than long and sclerites slightly divided on posterior portion from which small genital papillae produced in male, sternum small and triangular.

Mesosoma:

All tergites smooth on posterior of each tergite, sternites I-IV smooth and each provided with slit-like stigmata for book lungs.

Metasoma:

Cauda four times as long as carapace, first segment shorter than wide, segments I-IV with dorsal carinae crenulated, dentiform on posterior portion much more elevated on segment III and IV, dorsolateral carinae evenly crenulated, lateral carinae very weakly developed only on posterior portion of segment III-IV.

Fig.2. *Buthotus asimii*; A. carapace, dorsal view; B. padipalp, B1. femur, lateral view; B2. same, patella, lateral view; B3. same, manus, lateral view; C. fore leg, lateral view; D. telson, lateral view; E. pecten, ventral view; F. operculum, ventral view.

F.3. *Buthotus asimii*; A. aedeagus, lateral view; B. Electrophoresis of venom; C. Chromatography of venom.

Telson (Fig. 2D):

Telson with vesicle not as wide or deep as segment V, ventral surface smooth, ventral median crest not developed, sub-aculeus nodule absent, aculeus weakly curved, as short as vesicle.

Male Genitalia (Fig. 3A):

Flagellum 0.7 mm long, much elongated, elastic and flagellar-like, trunk 0.6 mm long, 0.12 mm wide, elongated, basally and medially dilated, pedicel 0.12 mm long, 0.13 mm wide, sperm spine short, spine-like, sperm tube short sclerotized.

Material examined:

Holotype, Male, Pakistan: Moro (Sindh), 17.4.95, leg. Asim Iftikhar lodged in MEMUK No. 4.
Paratypes: 9 females, other data same as holotype lodged at ZMUK.

Comparative note:

This new species is most closely related to *Buthotus alticola* (Birula) in having lateral eyes large, bulging, lateral ocular tubercles elevated but it can easily be separated from the same in having entire surface of carapace granular, 30 pectinal teeth are present and by the other characters as noted in the key and description.

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of Scorprian venom:

Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of Scorprian venoms were performed under denaturing condition using SDS (Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate) and B-Meresaphoethanol as denaturing agents MW-SDS-70L. Standard protein markers were used to prepare standard curve. The marker include, bovine serum albumin (66.0 KD a), egg albumin (45.0 KD a), glyceraldehyde-3-Phosphate, dehydrogenase, trypsinogen (24.1 KD a), trypsin inhibitor (20.1 KD a), and lactalbumin (14.2 KD a), *Buthotus asimii* venoms few broad bands in the molecular weight range of 70.0 KDa to 10.0 KDa and 50.0 KDa to 15.0 KDa.

Table 3. Specimens collected from various localities in Sindh.

Male	Female	Locality	Date of Collection	Temp.	Humidity	Collector
-	2	Tando Allahyar	3-8-94	34C°	75%	Rafat
-	1	Hala	24-8-94	29.5C°	78%	Rafat
I	-	Tandoadam	22-8-94	29.5C°	71%	Rafat
I	2	Hala	14-9-94	32C°	65C°	Sattar
I	1	Khipro	17-9-94	31.5C°	65%	Rafat
-	2	Tando Allahyar	19-9-94	32C°	65%	A.Fazal
I	-	Moro	17-4-95	36 C°	67%	Asim

Gel Filtration chromatography of Buthotus:

Venom (1000 mg) of *Buthotus asimii* sp.n., was loaded on sephadex G-50 column (2.5 x 90.00 cm) and eluted with 0.1 M. ammonium acetate buffer (PH 6.90). The venom was resolved into four peaks, two major (I and IV) and two moderate (II and III). Profile represents the presence of moderate to low molecular weight components.

DISCUSSION

The representatives of the genus *Buthotus* Vachon usually found in semidesert area of Palaeartic, Ethiopian and Oriental regions on equator. This genus plays sister group relationships with *Comsobuthus* by their synapomorphies like padipalp tarsus provided with three or four non-linear granules or a row of distal granules just proximal to terminal tooth but isolated from the same by its autapomorphies like lateral eyes large, bulging and lateral ocular tubercles elevated.

The present new species *Buthotus asimii* is very close to *B. alticola punjabensis* (Birula) by their synapomorphies viz. entire surface weakly granular and 32-pectinal teeth are present but by its autapomorphies like entire surface of carapace granular, 30-pectinal teeth are present and in male genitalia the flagellum is much elongated, basally and medially dilated help in discrimination of species.

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